

Literature Review on Human Capital and Company Sustainability

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Abstract:- This study looked at articles about intellectual capital, human capital, green environmental management, and the long-term success of a company to conclude the term of intellectual capital and Company Sustainability. This research was conducted with a sample Literature review with the topics of Intellectual Capital, Human Capital, Relational Capital or Customer Capital, Green Intellectual Capital, Green Human Capital, Green Structural Capital, Green Environmental Management, Company Sustainability. The source used is Google Scholar. Articles are selected based on predetermined keywords, then the contents are concluded.

Keywords:- Literature Review, Human Capital, Company Sustainability.

I. INTRODUCTION

A company's Green Intellectual Capital is an intangible asset that is very important because it helps the company stay alive and grow. This is called "corporate sustainability." In terms of protecting the environment, investing in intellectual capital or "Green Intellectual Capital" (GIC) has a lot to do with that (Ullah, 2021). GIC can help businesses improve their environmental management and competitiveness (Asiaei, K et al., 2021). GIC has a significant impact on the company's performance, which can help it stay in business for a long time. According to Josephine et al. 2020, Green Human Capital and Green Relational Capital affect Business Sustainability. Green Structural Capital doesn't affect business sustainability (Yusoff et al., 2021). This study looked at articles about intellectual capital, human capital, green environmental management, and the long-term success of a company to conclude the term of Intellectual capital and Company Sustainability.

II. METHODS

This research was conducted with a sample Literature review with the topics of Intellectual Capital, Human Capital, Relational Capital or Customer Capital, Green Intellectual Capital, Green Human Capital, Green Structural Capital, Green Environmental Management, Company Sustainability. The source used is Google Scholar. Articles are selected based on predetermined keywords, then the contents are concluded.

III. RESULT

➤ *Intellectual capital*

The term "intellectual capital" (IC) refers to all of the things in a company that can help it compete in the market, such as intellectual material knowledge, information, experience, and intellectual property, all of which can be used to make things better for people (Martin, 2011). To win the long-term competition, an organisation needs the power of IC, which is what the organisation needs to do so. It has human capital, structural capital, and relational capital in that order. IC is a lot of information that helps businesses run and beat their rivals at their jobs (Bontis, 2015). Human capital comprises employees who are very good at their jobs, are creative and intelligent, are experts in their field, and come up with new ideas and knowledge.

➤ *Structural Capital or Organizational Capital*

According to Omar et al. (2017), Structural Capital is the knowledge made clear in databases, programs, and systems organisation. This helps employees be more productive and effective at their jobs. According to Shih (2017), structural capital or organisational capital is the company's ability to get, share, and use knowledge. This is because processes, practices, and learning elements show how well the company can get, share, and use knowledge. To measure structural capital or organisational capital, Liu (2017) says that you can use indicators: employees realise that there is a link between their work and the Employees have a good understanding of the company's content culture. They know the company's perspective well. Employees can help each other and work together, and they have a lot of authority, responsibility, and benefits.

➤ *Relational Capital or Customer Capital*

According to de Leaniz and del Bosque (2013), relational capital is how well companies connect with important stakeholders like customers, suppliers, and outside partners. A company's relationship capital refers to how well it connects with other companies, such as how well it connects with other companies, how well it connects with other companies, how well it connects with other companies, and so on.

According to Liu (2017), the best way to measure relational capital is to look at these things: employees work together to solve problems, employees share information and learn from each other, employees interact and exchange ideas with people from different parts of the company, and employees work with customers, suppliers, partners, alliances, and so on to come up with solutions.

Based on what the experts say, they could say that relational capital, customer capital, or social capital, is something that helps businesses connect with investors, customers, suppliers, governments, or society positively.

➤ *Green Intellectual Capital*

According to Josephine *et al.* (2020), the definition of *Green Intellectual Capital* (GIC) is merging draft environment to in *Intellectual Capital* (IC) for compensating insufficiency previously to problem environment.

GIC reflects assets in no form of the owned company, including knowledge, wisdom, experience, and innovation in the protected area environment. With thus allow the company to obey regulation environment strict and fulfilling life enhancement awareness environment together consumer as well as create Mark for the company.

➤ *Green Human Capital*

According to (Josephine *et al.*, 2020), *green human capital* is defined as a presentation final on knowledge employees, expertise, competence, experience, behaviour, wisdom, creativity commitment on protection environment or *green innovation*. Moment this; a company no could ignore the aspect environment because it's essential to explore the role of *green human capital* and its effect on *business sustainability*. Based on the research above, it could conclude that the dimensions main of *green human capital* are the existence of caring *competence* and *behaviour* in governance environment life company.

➤ *Green Structural Capital*

When Josephine *et al.* say that green structural capital is an organisation's ability to back up power and authority and a company's culture of commitment and system management know-how, this is what they call "green structural capital." The company needs to build a solid foundation to deal with the challenges of climate change in Case determination internal policies (Grillitsch, 2019). It also needs to practice low carbon emissions management (Raar, 2015; Singh, 2015). People who work for the company will be happier and more productive if this is considered. Based on the research above, it might be possible to say that the most important aspects of green structural capital are the company's existence and its culture of caring for the environment.

➤ *Green Relational Capital*

According to (Josephine *et al.*, 2020), green relational capital is an interactive backup connection between customers, suppliers, members network, and top partners management environment and green innovation. Collaboration Among partners who can be trusted could Upgrade relationships and hope Among companies with customers. Mainly an organisation's manufacturing moves towards sustainable development by creating a close relationship with a supplier for Upgrading abilities, skills, and information to develop product new with more faster at more cost low, and then by positive affect business sustainability. Based on the research above, the dimensions of green relational capital are networking, and teamwork in realising cooperation in the management environment live.

A simple organisation owns three elements: people, cooperation, and goals. Three elements organisation the no stand up individually, will but each other relate, so that is one unified whole. Thus, as respondents in the study, managers and supervisors variable *green structural capital*, and the *green relational capital* represent organisation/company(Choi,2019).

➤ *Green Environmental Management*

Efforts that are systematic and integrated into nature to conserve the environment's function and prevent pollution and damage to the environment's life involves planning, utilising, controlling, maintaining, supervising, and enforcing the law. According to H. Younis & B. Sundarakani (2019). Green environmental management is defined as any activity, process, approach, or concept that can assist a business in achieving its environmental goals, adhering to environmental policies, anticipating the impact of operations on the environment, reducing waste and pollution before the implementation of existing regulations, or identifying positive methods for profiting from opportunity businesses through environmental enhancement. The environment of management becomes critical for a business or organisation, and many businesses are making strenuous efforts to develop green innovation and green designs. According to the research above, the primary elements of green environmental management are proactive green innovation and governance that goes beyond compliance environment life (Mojumder, A., & Singh, A)

➤ *Company Sustainability*

Continuity company is purposeful approach _ for creating Mark holder interest period long through the implementation of a business strategy that focuses on the dimensions social, environmental and economical in doing business.

➤ *Definition Company Sustainability*

Dembek *et al.* (2018) state that the corporation begins all actions with complete planning with the vision of sustainability, involving all stakeholders within and outside the organisation. As a development-oriented firm, the method ensures that all economic, social, and environmental factors are appropriately considered. Businesses extend their products and services responsibly by tapping into large economic, social, and ecological corridors.

Temporary Yusoff *et al.* (2019) describe continuity business as the purpose of a corporation to maximise profit and social development while taking environmental factors into account. Business sustainability begins with definition and development. It is sustained by public awareness and perception that natural resources are minimal and deleted if the natural limit is exceeded. As a result, man is in peril, catastrophe wreaking havoc on humanity. The firm that manages a business is critical in determining a person's performance in preserving the environment in perpetuity, sustaining business through resource supply, and neutralising residual economic activity (Purnama and Nawangsari, 2019). Based on research by Chow & Chen (2012) (Yusoff *et al.*, 2019) who revealed that *business sustainability* or continuity

business is something the work done by the company to minimise impact negative for the environment nor social for now and in the future and share organisational *sustainability* Becomes three aspect that is economical, social, and

environmental. *Sustainability* companies have dimensions and indicators To use to ensure continuity as listed in Table 1 as follows:

Table 1 Aspect Company Sustainability

No	Aspect	Best Effort
1	Economy	reduce input costs for the same output, Cooperation company with the government for protecting interest company, The company creates technology appropriate use that can be applied by profitable to the business unit other, Companies differentiate processes based on effort marketing from performance environment
2	Social	Company upgrade safety and health employee, Companies recognise and act on needs for fund initiative Public local, company show concern to aspect facility operation company, The company communicates impact risk environment on operation company to Public
3	Environment	The company reduces consumption energy, The company reduces waste and emissions from the operation, The company reduces the impact on species animals and natural habitats, The company reduces the use of ingredient burn traditional by replacing several source of energy that doesn't pollute, Company does action voluntarily, among other things however not limited to for restoration environment, do step for environmental audit, disclosure public, training employees and immunity

source: Yusoff *et al.*, (2019)

Based on opinion results study, then there are three dimensions main must _ fulfilled for explaining *sustainability* a company that is ability achievement well- being (aspect economy/profit), ability protect the environment (aspect environment/planet), and abilities Upgrade life social (aspect social / *people*).

IV. CONCLUSION

Intellectual capital refers to all of the things in a company that can help it compete in the market, such as intellectual material knowledge, information, experience, and intellectual property, all of which can be used to make things better for people *business sustainability* or continuity business is something the work done by the company to minimise impact negative for the environment nor social for now, In the future and share organisational *sustainability* Becomes three economic, social, and environmental aspects.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Asiaei, K., Bontis, N., Alizadeh, R., & Yaghoubi, M. (2021). Green intellectual capital and environmental management accounting: Natural resource orchestration in favor of environmental performance. *Business Strategy and the Environment*.
- [2]. Bontis, N., Janošević, S., & Dženopoljac, V. (2015). Intellectual capital in Serbia's hotel industry. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*.
- [3]. Choi, O. K., & Cho, E. (2019). The mechanism of trust affecting collaboration in virtual teams and the moderating roles of the culture of autonomy and task complexity. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 91, 305-315.
- [4]. de Leaniz, P. M. G., & del Bosque, I. R. (2013). Intellectual capital and relational capital: The role of sustainability in developing corporate reputation. *Intangible Capital*, 9(1), 262-280.
- [5]. Dembek, K., York, J., & Singh, P. J. (2018). Creating value for multiple stakeholders: Sustainable business models at the Base of the Pyramid. *Journal of Cleaner production*, 196, 1600-1612.
- [6]. Grillitsch, M., Hansen, T., Coenen, L., Miorner, J., & Moodysson, J. (2019). Innovation policy for system-wide transformation: The case of strategic innovation programmes (SIPs) in Sweden. *Research Policy*, 48(4), 1048-1061.
- [7]. Josephine, K., Ciptadi, B., & Aloysius, J. (2020). Pengaruh Green Intellectual Capital Terhadap Business Sustainability. *Jurnal Manajemen Strategi Dan Aplikasi Bisnis*, 3(2). <http://ejournal.imperiuminstitute.org/index.php/JMSA-B/article/view/261>
- [8]. Liu, C. H. (2017). Creating competitive advantage: Linking perspectives of organization learning, innovation behavior and intellectual capital. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 66, 13-23.
- [9]. Martín-de-Castro, G., Delgado-Verde, M., López-Sáez, P., & Navas-López, J. E. (2011). Towards 'an intellectual capital-based view of the firm': origins and nature. *Journal of business ethics*, 98(4), 649-662.
- [10]. Mojumder, A., & Singh, A. (2021). An exploratory study of the adaptation of green supply chain management in construction industry: the case of Indian Construction Companies. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 295, 126400.

- [11]. Omar, M. K., Mohd Yusoff, Y., & Kamarul Zaman, M. D. (2019). The effect of organizational learning capability as a mediating variable in the relationship between green intellectual capital and business sustainability: evidence from the manufacturing sector. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 9(6), 337-352.
- [12]. Shih, K. H., Chang, C. J., & Lin, B. (2010). Assessing knowledge creation and intellectual capital in banking industry. *Journal of intellectual capital*.
- [13]. Suseno, Y., & Pinnington, A. H. (2017). The war for talent: Human capital challenges for professional service firms. *Asia Pacific Business Review*, 23(2), 205-229.
- [14]. Ullah, H., Wang, Z., Mohsin, M., Jiang, W., & Abbas, H. (2021). Multidimensional perspective of green financial innovation between green intellectual capital on sustainable business: the case of Pakistan. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 1-17.
- [15]. Yusoff, Y. M., Omar, M. K., Zaman, M. D. K., & Samad, S. (2019). Do all elements of green intellectual capital contribute toward business sustainability? Evidence from the Malaysian context using the Partial Least Squares method. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 234, 626-637.
- [16]. Younis, H., & Sundarakani, B. (2019). The impact of firm size, firm age and environmental management certification on the relationship between green supply chain practices and corporate performance. *Benchmarking: An International Journal*.